

ISic3177

Fragment of a Greek epitaph

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Recovered in excavation in March 1952, seemingly in the area of the Hellenistic necropolis of contrada Cardusa ('trench 3')

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (near) Tripi, Current location unknown

Physical Description

Fragment of a cippus

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]μανικοῦ
2. [---]μία
3. [---]υροπῶλα

Apparatus

Text of Villard

Robert and Robert: [μ]υροπῶλα or [πορφ]υροπῶλα

Translation

Commentary

Villard appears to imply that this was also recovered from excavations in Trench 3 together with ISic3176 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3176>].

Villard states 'Roman period', but it is not clear why; SEG without explanation

states 'C1 BC (?)'. If the form of the letter pi is correctly recorded by Villard (short right hand hasta), then this would strongly suggest pre-Imperial, and in any event, the necropolis itself appears to go out of use in the earlier C2 BC, so the piece is hardly likely to be later than that.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645507

PHI 329721

Bibliography

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